

Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Leverage of Agricultural Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchanges

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Abstract

In financial management, an organization is always concerned about four major issues which are sources of finance, use of finance, investment decisions, and working capital management. Financial decisions have an influence on the ability of a corporation to remain a going concern since the wrong mix of debt and equity has short term and long-term implications. It is against this the current study examined the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of agricultural companies. Panel regression modelling revealed the positive influence of firm size and negative influence of tangibility, profitability and growth opportunities on the leverage of agricultural listed companies. Operating cash flows moderated the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of agricultural listed companies.

Key Words: Financial characteristics, Firm size, Profitability, Tangibility, Growth opportunities.

Introduction

In financial management, an organization is always concerned about four major issues which are sources of finance, use of finance, investment decisions and working capital management (Mwangi, 2016). Although all of them are important, leverage decision, which is a subset of sources of finance is more paramount for those companies operating in developing economies (Alghusni, 2015). Financial leverage decision is pivoted on stability levels of the social, both political and economic environment in which the company operates (Shubita & Alsawalhah, 2012).

Ambivalent studies have documented inconsistent findings on nexus between firm financial characteristics and leverage. For example, Bereznicka (2013) as well as Vergas, Cerqueira and Brandão (2015) for example reported a positive relationship between tangibility of assets and leverage. At Karachi Securities Exchange, Badar and Saeed (2013) and Mahnazmahdavi et al., (2013) reported an insignificant relationship between firm size and leverage.

An empirical examination of leverage in developing economies revealed that on average listed companies in Africa had 18% of long-term debt (Chen & Chen, 2011). According to Cui firm leverage in developing countries is a factor of firm size, tangibility, profitability, growth opportunity, and initial leverage. Also, there are external determinants of leverage which include individualism, uncertainty avoidance, no unilateral reorganization, management replacement, corruption, secured first and law enforcement.

Despite the extensive empirical literature on capital structure globally and locally, most of these studies have explored on factors affecting the capital structure (Githira & Nasieku, 2015; Wahome *et al.*, 2015; Mwangi, Makau & Kosimbei, 2014). Studies on the effect of firm characteristics on leverage in developing economies have also registered mixed findings. For instance, in their study, Mwangi and Birindu (2015) reported inverse and significant influence of asset tangibility on financial leverage. Wahome *et al.* (2015) found a positive and significant relationship between firm size and capital structure among insurance companies in Kenya. They further reported a positive and significant relationship between growth opportunities and leverage. The key question is despite agricultural role in economic development what has been the role of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of agricultural listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. To determine the influence of tangibility of assets on the leverage of non-financial agricultural listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.

- ii. To find out the influence of growth opportunities on the leverage of non-financial agricultural listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iii. To establish the influence of firm size on the leverage of non-financial agricultural listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- iv. To examine the influence of profitability on the leverage of non-financial agricultural listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.
- v. To evaluate the moderating effect of operating cash flows on the influence of financial characteristics on the leverage of non-financial agricultural listed firms at Nairobi Securities Exchange.

Literature Review

An investigation of the determinants of capital structure in Turkey was carried out by Acaravci (2015). By adopting panel data research design a sample of 79 listed companies from 1993 to 2010 were considered. Secondary data was collected from annual financial statements. Panel data analysis procedure was applied. Results of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between growth opportunities, size, profitability, tangibility, and leverage. While non-debt tax shield benefits had no significant influence on leverage. Since firm size had a negative influence on leverage it was concluded that the Turkish firms supported both pecking order theory and trade off theory.

A study to investigate the determinants of capital structure among non-financial firms listed in Portugal was brought forth by Vergas, Cerqueira and Brandão (2015). The panel research design was adopted and secondary data was collected from listed companies between 2005 to 2012. In the study capital structure was deemed to be affected by tangibility, profitability, and other sources of tax optimization, growth opportunities, and size and market valuation. A fixed effects regression model was fitted. Results of the study revealed an inverse relationship between profitability, firm size and leverage while growth opportunities, other sources of tax optimization both had a positive and significant relationship with leverage. These results were consistent with pecking order theory and trade off theory.

Acheampong, Agalega, and Shibu (2014) investigated the impact of financial leverage and market size on stock return in Ghana. Purposive sampling was used to select five companies which were actively trading in the manufacturing sector from 2006 to 2010. Ordinary least squares regression analysis was used to analyse the data and results of the study positive and significant relationship between stock return and financial leverage. These results were in support of agency theory since the management maximized on the agency costs associated with borrowed funds.

benefits were gained from borrowed capital. Moreover, there were minimal chances of undercapitalization since sales growth rate was catered by changes in the debt ratio and the management seemed to have adopted conservative working capital financing.

Hussan (2016) investigated the relationship between leverage and risk. In the study, leverage was operationalized as long-term debt financing while the risk was measured as changes in share price, sales revenue, and economic value added (EVA), earnings per share (EPS) and profitability (EBIT). Multiple regression analysis was revealed the positive and insignificant relationship between share price, sales revenue, profitability, and leverage while EPS and EVA had a negative and non-significant relationship with leverage. These findings disagreed with pecking order theory since an increase in profitability and sales revenues ought to have signaled to decrease in demand for external financing though the change may have led to increased market share which may call the need for more finances.

A Ghanaian case to investigate the effects of capital structure on profitability by Addae, Nyarko-Baasi, and Hughes (2013), through panel research design on a five-year period from 2005 to 2009. Results of the study revealed that most of the listed companies relied on short term to finance their enterprises. Thus, conservative working capital was the norm. Although, past studies had registered mixed findings; positive, neutral and negative the current study revealed an inverse relationship between profitability and capital structure and consequently supported pecking order theory. Even though the study adopted panel data it did not carry out stationarity, normality, heteroskedasticity and granger causality tests.

Mosavi et al., (2014) investigated the relationship between cash flow volatility and capital structure in Tehran securities exchange. The panel research design was adopted and purposive sampling was used to select 137 listed from 2006 to 2013. Operating cash flow was operationalized as natural logarithms of operating cash flow and the capital structure was measured as the ratio of long-term debt to total debt. Multiple regression analysis was used to analyze secondary data retrieved from annual financial statements. Results of the study revealed a negative and significant relationship between operating cash flow and capital structure. From the foregoing literature review, the following relationship was conceptualized.

Methodology

The study used panel data. Panel data is a series of multidimensional data where the behavior of entities are observed over time (Wooldridge, 2002). The key advantage of panel data is the ability to allow the researcher to control for variables that are not observable or measurable like culture and management practices over time but not across entities (Wooldridge, 2002). It was obtained from the NSE handbooks and from specific companies’ websites. As shown in the data collection sheet data on non-current assets, market prices, book value, turnover, total liabilities, profit after tax, operating cash flows were gathered. Secondary data was collected for period 2008-2016. Univariate and multivariate techniques were applied for data analysis. The influence was tested through the use of regression analysis and moderation was examined through an examination of marginal changes of slope coefficients due to the introduction of operating cash flows. The general models were of the form:

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 1}$$

The following regression model with the moderating variable was used for the analysis as proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986).

$$L_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_{i,t} + \beta_2 S_{i,t} + \beta_3 G_{i,t} + \beta_4 P_{i,t} + \beta_5 CF_{i,t} + CF_{i,t}(\beta_6 T_{i,t} + \beta_7 S_{i,t} + \beta_8 G_{i,t} + \beta_9 P_{i,t}) + \epsilon_j \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 2}$$

Where

L_{it} - total liabilities/total assets for each firm i at time t

T = Tangibility of assets, G =Growth opportunities, S =Firm size, P = Profitability, CF =Operating cash flows, β_i ($i=0,1,2,\dots,9$) are the associated regression coefficients, ϵ_j is the associated error term.

Findings and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

As shown in Table 4.1, the average tangibility average for agricultural listed companies was 70%. The minimum value was 22% and the maximum 93% and coefficient of skewness and -0.68. This negative skewness shows that asset tangibility was not normally distributed. Average profitability for agricultural firms was 8% with a standard deviation of 10%. The minimum profitability was (14%) and a maximum of 47%. Despite this wide variation, most agricultural firms were profitable within the period under consideration this was cemented by the skewness coefficient of 1.01. Although most agricultural quoted companies were profitable, wide variation can be a clear indication of performance instability which can be attributed to climatic changes. The average firm size 13.64, there was no wider variations in firm size as accounted for by minimum of 11.13 and maximum of 15.10. The average growth opportunity was 3.65 with a minimum of 0.15 and a maximum of 55.65. Growth opportunities were highly varied as accounted for by standard deviation of 10.32. The data was not normally distributed as accounted by the skewness coefficient of 3.84. Huge values of growth opportunities indicate that agricultural listed companies share prices contrasted market timing theory. The average ratio of total debt to total assets was 32% with one company being fully financed using debt capital. Skewness coefficient revealed that the most listed agricultural companies relied on debt financing as accounted for by Skewness coefficient of 2.90 units.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
T	58	0.22	0.93	0.70	0.15	-0.68	0.31
P	58	-0.14	0.47	0.08	0.10	1.01	0.31
S	58	11.13	15.10	13.64	1.41	-0.73	0.31
G	58	0.15	55.56	3.65	10.32	3.84	0.31
CF	58	-0.05	1.25	0.44	0.32	0.87	0.31
DTA	58	0.09	1.00	0.32	0.18	2.90	0.31

4.2 Diagnostic Results

4.2.1 Autocorrelation for Agricultural Companies Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.2, models with DTA response variable models, the F statistics were 150.576 and 475.524 with p values of 0.00 and 0.00 without and with moderation respectively. This, therefore, implies the presence of serial correlation. With the presence of the first order, serial correlation FGLS models were fitted.

Table 4.2 Wooldridge Test for Agricultural Companies Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent variable	Model	F (1,6)	Prob>F
DTA	Without moderator	150.576	0.000
	With moderator	475.524	0.000

4.2.1 Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Agricultural Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 4.3 presents the VIFs for the various study variables. The results indicate that the VIFs for all variables were less than 5 implying that the study data did not exhibit multicollinearity as recommended by (Gujarati, 2003).

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test Statistics for Agricultural Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
CF	1.87	0.535613
G	2.26	0.442084
T	1.66	0.602746
P	1.49	0.670851

S	1.31	0.761774
Mean VIF	1.72	

4.2.3 Heteroskedasticity Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Table 4.4 shows the likelihood ratio tests statistics for agricultural companies listed in NSE. The null hypotheses of the tests were that the error variance was homoscedastic for each model. The likelihood-ratio tests produced chi-square values of 8.59 with p-value 0.1265. This implies that the test was not significant at 5% level of significance hence the absence of heteroscedasticity.

Table 4.4 Heteroskedasticity Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Response Variable's models	Chi Square	Degree of freedom	P value
DTA	8.59	5	0.1265

4.2.4 Stationarity Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

The unit root test statistics for agricultural companies listed in NSE are presented in Table 4.5. From the table, it is evident that all variables are stationary at the level since the null hypothesis that all variables are not stationary at 5% significant level is rejected. This is further assurance on the robustness of the expected results. Further on, there was no need to differentiate the data.

Table 4.5 Stationarity Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Statistic	Value	p-value	
T	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	45.5256	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	-3.7231	0.000
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-4.3464	0.000
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	5.9578	0.000
P	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	32.8552	0.003
	Inverse normal	Z	-2.4186	0.008
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-2.7371	0.005
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	3.5633	0.000
G	Inverse chi-squared (84)	P	23.9678	0.046
	Inverse normal	Z	-2.5175	0.0065
	Inverse logit t (194)	L*	-3.555	0.0064
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	1.8837	0.030
CF	Inverse chi-squared (78)	P	36.8499	0.000
	Inverse normal	Z	2.3151	0.006
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	1.2619	0.893
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	-4.3512	0.000
S	Inverse chi-squared (78)	P	33.1666	0.003
	Inverse normal	Z	-2.0168	0.022
	Inverse logit t (199)	L*	-1.984	0.027
	Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	3.6222	0.000

4.2.5 Hausman Test Statistics for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.6, the Hausman test p value was greater than 0.05 for the model without and with a moderation which indicated that the random effects model ought to have been fitted.

Table 4.6 Hausman Test Statistics for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent variable	Model	Chi Square	df	P value
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DTA	Without moderator	3.02	4	0.555
	With moderator	3.65	4	0.455

4.2.7 Granger Causality Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.7, the p-values for all lagged financial characteristics (in isolation) values and DTA, run against DTA, are greater than 5% level of significance. This implies that the null hypotheses that individual financial characteristic does not granger cause leverage are not rejected for agricultural listed companies in NSE. When all lagged values of financial characteristics and DTA were run against DTA at the same time, the p value was zero. Being less than 5% level of significance, it means that the null hypothesis that financial characteristics do not granger causes leverage is rejected. It means that the financial characteristics of a firm, as a combination but not in isolation, can explain its leverage. When the lagged values of DTA and individual financial characteristic were run against individual financial characteristics values at the same time, the p value for T and G were less than 5% level of significance. The p values for S and P were greater than the said significance level. This implies that for T and G, the null hypotheses that leverage does not granger cause tangibility and growth are rejected at a 5% significance level.

Table 4.7 Granger Causality Test Results for Agricultural Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Dependent	Independent (Lagged)	F Statistic	P value
DTA	S,DTA	1.29	0.2896
	T,DTA	1.44	0.2458
	P,DTA	1.36	0.2618
	G,DTA	1.02	0.4404
	S,T,P,G,DTA	3.81	0.002
S	DTA,S	0.16	0.8485
T	DTA,T	0	0.9981
P	DTA,P	0.03	0.9737
G	DTA,G	0.3	0.7397

4.2.8 FGLS Regression Results of DTA as Dependent Variable with and without Moderator in Agricultural Firms Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.179, results on the effect of financial characteristics on debt financing for agricultural listed companies in NSE while operating cash flow was incorporated in the model show that the coefficient of SCF was -0.021 hence firm sizes had a negative influence on debt financing when the operating cash flow was incorporated. The p value was 0.726 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This shows that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on firm size was statistically insignificant on debt financing. The coefficient of TCF was -0.098 hence tangibility had a negative influence on debt as operating cash flow increased. The p value was 0.772 which is greater than the 5% level of significance. This indicates that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on tangibility was statistically insignificant on debt financing.

The coefficients of PCF and GCF were 0.062 and 0.017 respectively. This indicates that profitability and growth opportunities had a positive influence on debt respectively when operating cash flow was incorporated. The p values were 0.895 and 0.212 respectively to imply that the moderating influence of operating cash flow on profitability and growth opportunities were insignificant respectively on debt financing at 5% level of significance.

To further confirm the influence of the moderator, the coefficients of the model without the moderator are compared with the average marginal effect or change of financial characteristics on debt financing. If the two are different then there is moderation else no moderation. The marginal change shows how much debt changes by with an increase in one unit of the relevant financial characteristic when the average moderator value is

incorporated. This is achieved by differentiating model 2 in chapter three partially and incorporating the average moderating value as follows

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial T_{it}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 CF = -0.162 - 0.098 * 0.44 = -0.205$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial S_{it}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 CF = 0.046 - 0.021 * 0.44 = 0.036$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial P_{it}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 CF = 0.280 + 0.062 * 0.44 = 0.307$$

$$\frac{\partial STA_{it}}{\partial G_{it}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 CF = -0.016 + 0.0172 * 0.44 = -0.009.$$

Comparison between moderated and non-moderated variables with the operating cash flow revealed that it had a moderating influence on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the leverage of listed agricultural firms in NSE.

Table 4.8 FGLS Regression Results with and without Moderator in Agricultural Firms Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Without Moderation				With Moderation			
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	p>z
cons	.141	.112	1.26	.208	-.126	.356	-.35	.724
T	-.339	.066	-5.11	.000	-.162	.212	-.76	.447
S	.0302	.008	3.82	.000	.046	.022	2.06	.039
P	-.176	.088	-1.98	.047	.280	.416	.67	.501
G	-.001	.008	-1.32	.187	-.016	.015	-1.08	.279
CF					.138	.670	.21	.837
TCF					-.098	.340	-.29	.772
SCF					-.021	.061	-.35	.726
PCF					.062	.471	.13	.895
GCF					.017	.014	1.25	.212
	Wald chi ² (4) =37.35	R ² = 0.1860		P > Chi ² 0.00	Wald chi ² (9) =24.85	R ² = 0.3993		p>Chi ² .0000

Conclusion and Recommendations

It is recommended that if firms are seeking short term or long-term debt financing then there is need to revalue their assets since asset tangibility is the most preferred firm characteristics while seeking debt financing. To this far there is a need for capital market regulators to create more short-term financing debt instruments since it has a high potential of enhancing the profitability of listed companies. In addition, these short-term instruments should minimize borrowing cost but eliminate competition from alternative debt providers. Furthermore, capital market regulators should enhance the uptake of derivative financial through the use of futures and forwards this will reduce borrowing cost and enhance stakeholders' participation. Furthermore, creative financing would trigger the adoption of innovative financing products which would enhance management of borrowing costs without triggering control of demand and supply. Execution of such strategies would enhance non-listed financial company's debt planning and spread of financial risk and consequently minimize financial shocks emanating from debt financing.

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